

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF HYDROXYAPATITE NANOPARTICLES FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS

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Purpose of the study:

In this study, the synthesis of hydroxyapatite (HA) is reported. Currently, in addition to the traditional (oral and injection) methods of drug delivery to the body, delivery using some chemical means (micelles, liposomes, etc.) is more preferred by researchers. When using these tools, the advantages of such substances are that they can reduce the cytotoxicity of chemotherapeutic agents, reduce the amount of administered drugs, target delivery, and other features. In our studies, the nanopolymers used for drug delivery encountered some barriers in crossing the cornea of the skin. When HA nanoparticles were used they provided mechanical strength due to their crystalline structure. A hydrothermal synthesis method was used to synthesize HA nanoparticles.

Materials and methods:

Ca(NO₃)₂*2H₂O and (NH₄)₂HPO₄ (Sigma Aldrich) salts and hydrothermal synthesis method were used to synthesize HA nanoparticles. A mixture of Ca(NO₃)₂*2H₂O and (NH₄)₂HPO₄ salts (in a ratio of 0.4:0.1 moles, respectively) was dissolved in 20 mL of distilled water and stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 30 minutes at room temperature. The resulting solution had a pH of 3 (0.1 M HNO₃ was used to adjust the pH). After adding the acid, the clear solution turned into a colloidal suspension. The total volume of the suspension was reduced to 25 mL.

The reaction was allowed to proceed for 72 hours at 60 °C. After completion of the reaction, the resulting product was collected by centrifugation (10000 rpm, 10 minutes, 3 times). The obtained precipitate was washed with ethyl alcohol and dried in an oven at room temperature.

Results:

In this study, HA particles were synthesized using the hydrothermal method. Our team modified this method by changing the temperature and reagent concentration. These modifications have been used to produce HA nanoparticles ranging in size from nanometers to micrometers. Under optimized conditions, we were able to obtain HA nanoparticles with a hydrodynamic size distribution of approximately 270 nm (Figure 1). The synthesized HA nanoparticles were first screened using a zeta-sizer to measure their hydrodynamic size. The size and morphology of HA nanoparticles were analyzed using a SEM instrument (Jeol JSM-IT200LA) at the Uzbekistan-Japan Youth Innovation Center.

Conclusions:

In conclusion, it can be said that when the carrier drug was bound to HA nanoparticles, it was observed that the mechanical strength was improved compared to the previous state. Of course, this strength was found to depend on the particle size of the HA nanoparticles, and further research aimed to develop nanoparticles of higher quality using other synthesis methods.